

Synthesis, characterisation and catalytic activity of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]^{2+}$ bound to zirconium arsenophosphate

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The complex cation $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]^{2+}$ (CuT) has been anchored onto an inorganic ion exchanger, zirconium arsenophosphate (ZAsP), abbreviated as (ZAsP-CuT). Its catalytic activity has been studied for the disproportionation of hydrogen peroxide at different temperatures, different hydrogen peroxide concentration and for different amounts of the catalyst. The results show that it can be used as a promising catalyst for oxidation reactions.

Heterogenised homogeneous catalysis has emerged as a new type of catalysis having advantages of both homogeneous catalysis (specificity, activity) and heterogeneous catalysis, (easy removal of catalyst from products). In catalysis, these materials are regarded as 'Third generation catalysts'¹.

Metal complexes have been affixed to polymers and to oxide surfaces². They have also been encapsulated in zeolite cavities³ and between the layers of a smectite clay⁴. Of the methods available for anchoring, the ion exchange method of catalyst immobilisation is most simple. The attractiveness of the method is further increased by providing temperature and solvent stable supports. The supports generally used are organic polymers or inorganic oxides. However, inorganic ion exchangers of the class of tetravalent metal acid (tma) salts⁵ serve as ideal supports in heterogenised homogeneous catalysis as these materials besides possessing high thermal and chemical stability, are cation exchangers. We reported^{6,7} catalytic activity of transition metal ions and metal complexes supported on various zirconium based inorganic ion exchangers, which involves only single salts. It was therefore thought of interest to examine the catalytic activity of mixed tma salts.

In the present endeavour a typical heterogenised homogeneous catalyst, ZAsP-CuT has been synthesized by anchoring $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]^{2+}$ (CuT) onto zirconium arsenophosphate (ZAsP). The resulting compound has been characterized by elemental analysis, thermal analysis, FTIR, ESR, reflectance spectroscopy and surface area measurements (BET method). The catalytic activity has been studied for the disproportionation of hydrogen peroxide at different temperatures, different concentrations of H_2O_2 and different amounts of the catalyst.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis indicate the composition of ZAsP to be 1 : 1 : 1.

TGA of ZAsP indicates the presence of hydrated water which is lost very slowly at 200°. There is no evidence for the decomposition of the solid within the temperature range of 1000°. TGA of ZAsP-CuT shows break in the temperature range 300–400°, which may probably be due to the decomposition of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]^{2+}$ from the surface of the support.

FTIR spectra of ZAsP show broad bands at ~3400 (asym and sym OH and aquo OH) and a sharp medium band at ~1620 cm^{-1} (aquo H–O–H bending). A number of strong and sharp bands at ~800, ~1000, ~1400 and ~1500 cm^{-1} are attributed to the Zr–O stretching, and the presence of HPO_4^{2-} , HAsO_4^{2-} , PO_4^{3-} and AsO_4^{3-} groups, respectively. The spectra also give an indication of the presence of complex on the support. However, a quantitative interpretation is not possible due to strong coupling between various vibration modes. The spectrum of the complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4](\text{NO}_3)_2$ consists of sharp bands at 3300 and 1600 cm^{-1} , attributed to the NH stretching and bending modes, respectively. The spectrum of ZAsP-CuT shows broad bands at ~3400–300 cm^{-1} and a strong band at 1600 cm^{-1} . This spectrum is almost identical to that obtained for ZAsP. This may be attributed to the merging of OH and NH stretching and bending modes respectively.

The reflectance spectra of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]\text{NO}_3$ show a broad band at 600 nm, and $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]^{2+}$ sorbed on ZAsP shows a broad band at 800 nm. Shift in λ_{max} may be attributed to a slight distortion in the geometry around the Cu centre due to the sorption of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]$ on ZAsP.

The ESR spectra of the complex sorbed on ZAsP is

similar to that of the complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4](\text{NO}_3)_2$ in solid state. The g_{av} value of bound complex (2.116) is slightly less as compared to that of complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4](\text{NO}_3)_2$ (2.126). This shows that there is a slight change in geometry of the support-bound complex as compared to the free complex. Similar observation was reported earlier⁸.

In the present investigation, the kinetic analysis is based on the initial rate data because the reaction rate approaches equilibrium after a time lapse. It has been found that the rate is independent of initial concentration of hydrogen peroxide (from 5 to 10 vol.; the rate was $\sim 2.86 \times 10^{-4}$ K min^{-1}). An increase in the amount of catalyst from 0.025 to 0.075 g, increased the rate of reaction from 1.28×10^{-4} to 3.56×10^{-4} K min^{-1} . An increase in the reaction temperature in the range 25–40°, increased the rate of reaction from 1.62×10^{-4} to 3.78×10^{-4} K min^{-1} .

The colour of surface-adsorbed complex ion changed from blue to greenish yellow when it came in contact with H_2O_2 . The colour persisted as long as any residual hydrogen peroxide remained undecomposed. After complete decomposition of the H_2O_2 , the catalyst regained its original blue colour. This could be due to the formation of a peroxo species⁸.

Based on the above observation the following reaction mechanism and rate equation have been suggested, as proposed by us earlier⁷. It is known that H_2O_2 dissociates to^{9,10},

The surface amine complex may interact with HO_2^- ion to form an intermediate complex,

A second molecule of H_2O_2 may then interact with the intermediate complex to form the products,

The value of energy of activation (Arrhenius plot) is 11.80 kcal mol^{-1} . The activity of the complex is attributed to the formation of stable ternary complex between the Cu-complex and an oxygen donor. In other words, the activity may be attributed to the formation of an intermediate peroxo species. Besides, when a metal complex is bound to a support, its motion is restricted. Reactions on such catalysts are expected to be more rapid than in the catalyst molecules which are free¹⁰.

Experimental

Zirconium oxychloride, disodium arsenate, ammonium molybdate, hydrogen peroxide, copper(II) nitrate (A.R. grade) were used as received.

ZAsP was prepared by mixing zirconium oxychloride (0.1 mol, 100 ml), disodium arsenate (0.1 mol, 100 ml) and trisodium orthophosphate (0.1 mol, 100 ml) in 1 : 1 : 1 ratio with continuous stirring. The pH of the mixture was adjusted to ~ 1 by adding nitric acid or ammonium hydroxide as appropriate with constant stirring. The gel thus obtained was kept at room temperature overnight, filtered, washed with conductivity water and dried at 100°. For kinetic studies, the dried material was broken down to the desired particle size. It was converted to the hydrogen form by immersing in 1 M HNO_3 overnight, then washed several times with conductivity water, filtered and dried at 100°.

Anchoring of $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]^{2+}$ on ZAsP : A known concentration of complex ion solution $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]^{2+}$ was added to the acid-treated ion exchanger (1 g) and set aside for 24 h with intermittent shaking. It was then filtered, washed with conductivity water and dried at 100°. The concentration of Cu^{2+} ion present on the exchanger was estimated by iodometric method.

Kinetic studies : A weighed quantity of the catalyst was shaken with H_2O_2 (10 ml; 5 vol.) in a thermostat at 30°. The volume of oxygen evolved was measured at various time intervals and also after complete decomposition of hydrogen peroxide using a gas burette. Experiments were carried out at different temperatures in the range 30–40°. The influence of various quantities of the catalyst (0.025–0.075 g) and varying the concentration (5–10 vol.) of hydrogen peroxide was studied at 35°. The sample was analysed for Zr, As and P by the reported methods¹¹. Thermogravimetric analysis of samples were performed on a Shimadzu DT 30 analyser at a heating rate of 10°/min. FTIR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 1720 spectrophotometer, and reflectance spectra on a Shimadzu PR-1 instrument using barium sulphate as reference. ESR spectra were recorded at room temperature using a Varian E-15 spectrometer and the values reported being relative to TCNE standard with $g = 2.00277$.

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